

Potential Anti-Cancer Agents. Synthesis of Nitrogen Mustards

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Manuscript received 17 June 1976; revised 25 October 1976; accepted 30 December 1976

3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-(4'-N, N-bis-dichloroethyl amino hydrochloride benzoyl) butyric acid; 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-(N, N-bis-dichloroethyl amido) butyric acid; 1-(N,N-bis-dichloroethyl)-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-(4'-methoxy benzoyl) butyryl amide & 1-(N, N-bis-dichloroethyl)-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl) valeramide have been synthesised in view of their potential antitumour activities. The structures of these nitrogen mustards were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, I. R. and N.M.R. spectral data.

SINCE the concept of pharmacologically active substances being composed of an active moiety and carrier moiety was first put forward by Ing¹, a host of compounds carrying cytostatically active alkylating functions such as nitrogen mustards in combination with a carrier moiety have been synthesised.

The carrier moieties used by us were the various aromatic derivatives of butyric acid. Compound I carrying the mustard group functionality on the benzoyl ring was synthesised and compared favourably with the structure of chlorambucil², one of the important drugs in the treatment of human neoplasm. Further, many workers have sought latent forms of nitrogen mustard derivatives possessing the high carcinolytic activity of the parent compound but having a greatly reduced general toxicity. The clinical importance of such nitrogen mustards^{3,4} and selectivity of action of various amides⁵⁻⁷ which on enzymic hydrolysis *in vivo* gave tumour growth inhibitory di-2-chloroalkylamines, encouraged us to synthesise some amides of the type II, IX and X to evaluate them for antitumour activity.

Compound I was obtained by the condensation of N,N-bis-dichloroethyl aniline on 3-aryl glutaric anhydride in a Friedel-Crafts reaction. I.R. γ in cm^{-1} (KBr): 2700-3200 (OH; broad); 1700 (C=O of COOH); 1660 (Arom. C=O); 2300, 2600 (tert. amine salt); 1400 ($>\text{N}^+-\text{CH}_2^-$); 1305 ($\text{C}_{ar,om}-\text{N}$); 760 (C-Cl); 1605, 1505, 830 (*p*-subst. phenyl) and 1580 (gr. containing *p*-or π electrons are in conjugation).

Compound II was obtained by condensing 3-aryl glutaric anhydride with N,N-bis-dichloroethylamine in chloroform. I.R. γ in cm^{-1} (Nujol): 2800-3200 (OH; broad); 1705 (C=O of -COOH); 1650 (C=O of tert. amide) and 760 (C-Cl). N.M.R. δ (CDCl_3): proton *d* at 2.3, doublet of *e* at 2.6, doublet of *c* at 2.75, *b* at 2.9, *a* at 3.25, *g* at 3.8, *f* at 5.2 (which collapsed on D_2O exchange) and aromatics at 6.8-7.3 δ .

The precursor for the target compound (IX) was 3-aryl-4-aroyl butyric acid⁸ (III). Conversion of III into V was achieved by treatment with thionyl chloride in benzene. I.R. spectrum (Nujol) did not show the presence of absorption in the region 2800-3200 cm^{-1} (H-bonded OH; broad) and N.M.R. spectrum (CDCl_3) was not having a signal due to acidic proton at 14.17 δ . While the appearance of the C-Cl band at 760 cm^{-1} and keto group of $-\text{COCl}$ at 1780 cm^{-1} (shift to the higher frequencies due to the -I effect of chlorine) in I.R. and the shift of *c* protons doublet to the downfield at 5.7 δ (due to the deshielding by the chlorine atom), in N.M.R. was shown.

Formation of VII was effected by the action of diethanolamine on V in chloroform. The I.R. spectrum (thin film) showed the presence of a broad absorption in 3200-3500 cm^{-1} (characteristic of -OH gr.) and tert. amide band at 1650 cm^{-1} while a band at 760 cm^{-1} assigned to the ν C-Cl in the parent compound disappeared. In N.M.R. spectrum (CDCl_3) the four *b* protons resonate at 1.3 δ while four *a* protons together with the two sets of two proton resonance (of parent compound) form a complex pattern of signals in the 1.7-3.1 δ region, the two hydroxyl protons resonate at 4.7 δ .

Chlorination of VII by thionyl chloride in benzene gave final compound IX. In the I.R. spectrum (Nujol), significant is the presence of C-Cl band at 760 cm^{-1} while the broad band at 3000-3500 cm^{-1} (characteristic of hydroxyl group) disappeared. N.M.R. spectrum (CDCl_3) did not show the signal due to the protons of hydroxyl groups but showed the shifting of *a* protons to the down field (due to the deshielding by the chlorine atom), at 4.9 δ .

In the synthesis of the compound X, 3,5-diaryl valeric acid (IV) was used as a starting material which was obtained by the reduction of carbonyl group of the aroyl butyric acid (III). The reduction was effected by the Huang-Minlon modification⁹ of the Wolff-Kishner reduction. The I.R. spectrum (KBr) of this compound revealed the disappearance of aromatic C=O stretching (of precursor compound) indicates its reduction into $>\text{CH}_2$. In N.M.R. (CF_3COOH) two sets of two protons resonance, indicates the presence of another set of two protons, thus confirming the reduction of the carbonyl group (protons *e* at 2, *f* at 2.5 and *c* at 3 δ).

X was obtained following the same sequence of reactions as were used in the synthesis of IX, through the formation of the intermediates VI and VIII, starting from the reduced acid IV.

I.R. spectrum (thin film) of VI did not show the presence of broad absorption in the region 2800-3200 cm^{-1} (characteristic of the hydroxyl group) but showed the presence of ν C-Cl at 760 and ν C=O at 1780 cm^{-1} (shift to the higher frequencies due to the -I effect of chlorine). N.M.R. spectrum (CDCl_3) of VI exhibited a shift downfield (5.7 δ) of the *c* protons (due to the deshielding by the chlorine atom) and disappearance of the acidic proton.

I.R. spectrum (thin film) of VIII revealed the presence of a broad absorption in 3200-3500 cm^{-1} region (characteristic of hydroxyl group), band at 1650 cm^{-1} for tert. amide but the disappearance of ν C-Cl from 760 cm^{-1} . N.M.R. spectrum (CDCl_3) showed additional signals due to the protons *b* and *a* at 1.3 and 2.85 δ respectively, while the hydroxyl protons at 4.7 δ .

I. R. spectrum (thin film) of X showed the appearance of ν C-Cl at 760 cm^{-1} and the disappearance of the broad band from the region 3200-3500 cm^{-1} (due to the hydroxyl group of the parent compound). N. M. R. spectrum (CDCl_3) exhibit the

shifting of *a* protons to the downfield (4.15 δ) due to the deshielding by the chlorine atom, but no hydroxyl protons.

Compounds I, II, IX and X have been submitted to the National Cancer Institute, National Institute of Health, Department of Health, Education and Welfare, Bethesda, Maryland (U. S. A.) for antitumour testing and their results will be published elsewhere.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded on a Gallenkamp Melting Point Apparatus and are uncorrected. T. L. C. was carried out on plates coated with silica gel (Merck Kieselgel G) while silica gel (mesh 60-120) was used for column chromatography.

3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-(4',-N, N-bis-dichloroethyl-amino hydrochloride benzoyl) butyric acid (I): 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) glutaric anhydride (2.2 g; 0.01 m) and N, N-bis-dichloroethylaniline (2.18 g; 0.01 m) were dissolved in 40 ml of CS_2 . Anhydrous AlCl_3 (3 g; 0.067 m) was slowly added to the stirred solution. Stirring was continued for 6 hrs at room temp. and the reaction mixture was left overnight. CS_2 was distilled off and the residual mass was transferred to the vigorously stirred solution of concentrated HCl in crushed ice. The separated solid was extracted with ether and recrystallised from xylene. The compound was further purified by chromatographing it over silica gel with a mixture of ethyl acetate and benzene (8:2) as an eluent. m.p. 186°. Yield, 2 g (40%).

Anal: Found: C, 54.6; H, 5.3; N, 2.91 and Cl, 23.98%.

Calcd: for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{NO}_4\text{Cl}_3$: C, 54.5; H, 5.4; N, 2.89 and Cl, 24.02%.

3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-(N, N-bis-dichloroethylamido) butyric acid (II): 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) glutaric anhydride (2.2 g; 0.01 m) and N, N-bis-dichloroethylamine (1.42 g; 0.01 m) were refluxed in 30 ml of chloroform for half an hr. White crystals, separated on cooling, were recrystallised from chloroform twice to get a pure compound. m.p. 172°C. Yield, 2.53 g (70%),

tlc. chloroform-benzene (5:5).

Anal: Found: C, 52.89; H, 5.72; N, 3.89 and Cl, 19.54%.

Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}_4\text{Cl}_2$: C, 53.05; H, 5.84; N, 3.87 and Cl, 19.57%.

3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-(4'-methoxybenzoyl) butyryl chloride (V): 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-(4'-methoxybenzoyl) butyric acid (III) (1.57g; 0.005 m) was refluxed with 10 ml of thionyl chloride in 20 ml of benzene for 3 hrs. Excess of thionyl chloride was distilled off along with benzene to get a low melting compound. The compound was purified by column chromatography,

using chloroform-benzene (6 : 4) as an eluent and silica gel as an adsorbent. Yield, 2.34 g (71%).

tlc. Ethyl acetate-chloroform (9 : 1).

Anal : Found : C, 65.72 ; H, 5.49 and Cl, 10.10%.

Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{19}O_4Cl$: C, 65.80 ; H, 5.52 ; and Cl, 10.22%.

1-(*N, N*-bis-diethanol)-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-(4'-methoxybenzoyl) butyryl amide (VII) : 3.46 g ; 0.01 m of V and 2.1 g ; 0.02 m of diethanolamine were refluxed with 20 ml of chloroform for 6 hrs. Cooled and washed with water to remove excess of diethanolamine. Dried on anhydrous sodium sulphate. 3.54 g (87%) of heavy oil was separated by addition of petroleum ether from chloroformic solution. It was then purified by passing through a column of silica gel using ethyl acetate-chloroform mixture (6 : 4) as an eluent.

Anal : Found : C, 66.60 ; H, 7.0 ; and N, 3.41%.

Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{29}NO_6$: C, 66.49 ; H, 7.04 and N, 3.37%.

1-(*N, N*-bis-dichloroethyl)-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-(4'-methoxybenzoyl) butyrylamide (I.V) : 2.01 g ; 0.005 m of VII was refluxed with 20 ml of thionyl chloride and 30 ml benzene for 4 hrs. Excess of thionyl chloride was distilled off along with benzene. Semisolid mass was triturated with ethanol. Analytical grade sample was obtained by chromatographing it over silica gel and using chloroform-benzene (7 : 3) as an eluent. Yield, 3.42 g (75%).

Anal : Found : C, 60.90 ; H, 6.02 ; N, 2.99 and Cl, 15.72%.

Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{27}NO_4Cl_2$: C, 61.08 ; H, 5.99 ; N, 3.10 and Cl, 15.68%.

3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl) valeric acid (IV) : A mixture of III (6.56 g ; 0.02 m), KOH (4g), diethylene glycol (30 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (85% ; 25 ml) was refluxed for a period of 1 1/2 hrs. The condenser was then removed and the flask heated till the reaction mixture attained a temp. of 195-200°. At this stage, the condenser was replaced and the mixture was refluxed for a further period of 4 hrs. The solution was cooled, diluted with water and poured with stirring into 15 ml of 6*N* HCl. Recrystallisation from benzene gave 5.46 g (83%) of IV. m. p. 157°C.

tlc. ethylacetate-benzene (6 : 4)

Anal : Found : C, 72.50 and H, 6.39%.

Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{29}O_4$: C, 72.59 and H, 7.06%.

3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl) valeryl chloride (VI) : Adopting the similar procedure as was used in the synthesis of V, 2.2 g (73%) of low melting compound VI was obtained. It was then purified by

passing through a silica gel column, using ethylacetate-benzene mixture (5 : 5) as an eluent.

Anal : Found : C, 68.41 ; H, 6.50 and Cl 10.50%.

Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{21}O_3Cl$: C, 68.56 ; H, 6.36 and Cl, 10.65%.

1-(*N, N*-bis-diethanol)-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl) valeramide (VIII) : Similar procedure, followed to obtain VII, was applied to get VIII. 3.89 g (85%) of heavy oil was obtained on addition of petroleum ether in the chloroformic solution. It was purified by passing through a column, using silica gel as an adsorbing material and ethylacetate-chloroform mixture (8 : 2) as an eluent.

Anal : Found : C, 68.86 ; H, 7.94 and N, 3.45%.

Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{31}NO_5$: C, 68.80 ; H, 7.78 and N, 3.49%.

1-(*N, N*-bis-dichloroethyl)-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl) valeramide (X) : Following the procedure adopted for the synthesis of IX, X was obtained. Analytical grade sample was obtained by chromatographing it over silica gel using chloroform-benzene mixture (6 : 4) for elution. Yield, 3.23 g (73%).

Anal : Found : C, 62.90 ; H, 6.59 ; N, 3.20 and Cl, 16.10%.

Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{29}NO_3Cl_2$: C, 63.01 ; H, 6.61 ; N, 3.20 and Cl, 16.18%.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Dr. Govindachari and Dr. Grewal, CIBA Research Centre⁴ for NMR and Dr. Padhye, UDCT, Bombay for IR spectra. One of the authors (DNC) is grateful to UGC, New Delhi for awarding a JRF.

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